

UDK.338.24

THE STRATEGY FOR TRANSITIONING TO A "GREEN" ECONOMY: NECESSITIES, CHALLENGES, AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada Ozbekiston iqtisodiyotini yashillashtirish istiqbollari, "Yashil" iqtisodiyotga otish strategiyasi, maqsad va vazifalari, yashil iqtisodiyot – yashil taraqqiyot Ozbekistonda Yashil iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish bosqichlari haqida soʻz boradi.

Tayanch iboralar: Yashil iqtisodiyot, iqtisodiy- ijtimoiy, ekologik, energetik, modernizasiya, konfrensiyada, aksiomalar, yoqilgʻi – energetik resurslar, atrof – muhit muxofazasi, infratuzilma, konsepsiya, energiya samaradorlik.

Abstract: This article discusses the prospects of developing the Uzbek economy towards sustainability, the strategy for transitioning to a "Green" economy, its objectives and tasks. The concept of "Green Economy - Green Development" in Uzbekistan, as well as the stages of shaping and developing a green economy in the country, are addressed.

Keywords: Green economy, socio-economic, ecological, energy, modernization, conference, axioms, fossil fuels, atmosphere, infrastructure, concept, energy efficiency.

Introduction: In today's world, achieving innovative progress, modernizing the economy, and maximizing the efficient use of limited resources are not only important tasks for national economies but also global priorities. The current economic system should not only be based on economic growth, technological advancement, and competitive strategies but also ensure improved living conditions for every individual and create favorable economic conditions for future generations. Such a transformation of the economy is now referred to as sustainable development based on a "Green Economy." The main goal of this study is to analyze the essence of a green economy and identify the prospects for developing the economy in Uzbekistan in line with the principles of sustainability. [L.1;2]

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Discussions and limitations. It is well known to all of us that the surrounding environment is an essential element and a factor in every stage of economic development. The harmonious relationship between nature and the economy is reflected in the concept of green economy. Green economy, developed in the last twenty years, is an economic and social direction that considers the economy as an independent component of the natural environment, forming and developing within the natural environment. The main task of the green economy is to transform production and consumption processes in an ecologically sustainable manner (ecologization).

The prospects for developing the economy of Uzbekistan are limited by the extent to which the economic impact and progress can be expanded in an unsustainable natural environment. Resources cannot meet endless needs in a limited condition. All situations and systems on Earth (including the natural and economic environment) are interconnected. The theory of green economy is based on the following three axioms:

The main reason for the widespread acceptance of the theory of green economy today is the global significance of existing environmental issues and the need to address these issues while meeting the population's demands for goods and services proposed by the green economy. According to a UNEP report on the green economy, if 2% of the world's GDP is spent on greening the economy, long-term sustainable economic growth can be achieved, and one of the most important aspects is that it can simultaneously address climate conditions and water scarcity issues. The 1992 Rio de Janeiro conference played a significant role in the international and national economic systems' widespread adoption of the green economy direction. The main topic discussed at this conference was minimizing the damage caused to the environment in the process of economic development. In this city, during the conference, a document was signed, placing an obligation to ensure the sustainable modernization of national economic systems on the agenda of the next conference, under the auspices of the desired future. [L.3;,5]

Results Expected from Research. The findings from conducted research analyses indicated the existence of interrelated issues and needs in ensuring efficient, resource-efficient, and environmentally safe economy in the context of climate change. Internationally, the concept of "green" economy is considered as a fundamental solution that directly contributes to human development by addressing ecological, energy, food, and economic challenges. [L.2;,4;,6]

The goals and objectives of the Green Economy Transition Strategy are as follows: to reduce emissions from heating gas plants by 10% compared to the level in 2010; to increase the energy efficiency indicator by two times and decrease the carbon footprint of overall energy consumption; to further develop renewable energy sources and increase their share in the total electricity production by more than 25%; to ensure

that 100% of the population and economic sectors have access to modern, affordable, and reliable energy; to modernize industrial facilities in our country, increase energy efficiency by at least 20%, and promote the use of clean and environmentally friendly technologies and industrial processes; to develop and expand electric transportation, as well as improve the energy efficiency and environmental characteristics of motor vehicles and public transport; to significantly increase the water use efficiency in all sectors of the economy, implement irrigation technologies covering up to 1 million hectares and increase the crop productivity by a certain percentage; to achieve a neutral balance in land degradation; and to increase the average productivity of basic agricultural food products by a certain percentage. [L.4;,5;,6]

The primary directions of implementing the Green Economy Transition Strategy in the basic sectors of the economy include improving energy efficiency, diversifying energy resources, and utilizing renewable energy sources, adapting to climate change and mitigating its consequences, enhancing the efficiency of natural resource utilization, and promoting environmental conservation. The strategy also includes the development of financial and legal mechanisms to support and promote the "green" economy. Improving the ecological safety of transportation vehicles is considered one of the important stages of innovatively modernizing the economy in Uzbekistan. In this regard, measures have been planned and implemented to increase the energy efficiency of vehicles used in the transportation sector, promote the use of green alternative fuels, and introduce green electric vehicles. The widespread use of solar-powered vehicles contributes to a reduction in the volume of various pollutants emitted into the environment, leading to improved urban ecotourism. [L.6;,7]

Green economy - Green development To achieve green development, it is necessary to transition to a green economy and further develop it. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a green economy in our country to shape such an economy. The concept of the green economy emerged at the end of the last century as a direction in economic sciences. It is considered as an integral part of the natural environment and is one of its directions. The concept of the green economy encompasses ecological economics related to nature and society, environmental economics, resource-based economics, population development, and feminist economics. The green economy is an economic system aimed at developing all sectors of the economy together with the preservation of our planet's ecology and sustainable use of necessary resources for human life and health. To achieve this, the following measures need to be implemented:

- Firstly, it is necessary to increase the creation of material goods to meet the needs of the population, improve their well-being, living standards, and quality without causing harm to the environment and ecology.

- Secondly, in the field of production and economic development, energy resources are needed. Work should be carried out in areas such as increasing the share of renewable energy sources, converting public transportation to electric power, and implementing energy-efficient building practices.

Given the current level of utilization of fossil fuel energy resources in Uzbekistan, it is evident that meeting the country's energy needs in an environmentally friendly manner by increasing the use of renewable and alternative energy sources is one of the important issues in the process of economic development. Furthermore, it is worth noting, as mentioned in the report of the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific, that future development relies on the utilization of energy forms that are safe, sustainable, reliable, continuously available, environmentally friendly, and provide opportunities for utilization without causing harm to the environment.

In terms of solar energy potential in Uzbekistan, if the total capacity of solar energy is equivalent to millions of tons of oil (mtoe), the total capacity of wind energy is estimated at 2.2 mtoe. Several improvements have been made in this field in our country. [L.1;;2;;7;;8]

In conclusion

In conclusion green economy is a system that involves the environmentally friendly production and provision of goods and services using available resources efficiently. The main reason for the widespread adoption of the concept of green economy today is its ability to address global environmental issues and simultaneously resolve existing issues by meeting the population's demand for green products and services. Promoting green economy in Uzbekistan enables further utilization of natural resources, addressing various ecological issues, and creating conditions for sustainable economic growth while enhancing the eco-friendliness of the population.

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